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Innovative in Service Sector Enterprises Financing of Activities

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***Abstract:** This article analyzes effective methods and models of financing innovative activities in the service sector. The service sector is characterized by its continued rapid growth and its innovative development occupies an important place in the global economy. The article presents the theoretical foundations of innovative financing methods, financial mechanisms and international experiences (USA, Europe, China). In financing the service sector, approaches such as venture capital, state grants, fintech platforms and crowdfunding are often used. The article also discusses the problems and opportunities in financing innovative activities in Uzbekistan. At the end of the article, recommendations are presented on effective mechanisms for financing innovative activities for the service sector, cooperation between the public and private sectors, as well as the use of international experiences.*

***Key words:** Innovative activities, service sector, financing methods, venture capital, crowdfunding, fintech, state grants, international experiences, innovation in uzbekistan. star border.*

1. Introduction

The service sector has become an integral part of the global economy in the 21st century, and the sector is characterized by rapid development. New technologies, digital platforms, and innovative approaches are changing the shape of the service industry, leading to major changes in the simplification of the processes of production and delivery of services. However, the financial resources needed to introduce innovation in the service sector are often insufficient. Creating innovations and putting them into practice poses significant risks and financial barriers for many businesses.

Financing of innovation for the service sector, especially for small and medium-sized businesses, is a serious problem in many countries. Developing and implementing the most efficient financing

mechanisms is of importance to stimulate economic growth, create new jobs and increase competitiveness. The rapidly changing and highly competitive service sector market requires increased collaboration between the public and private sectors in the process of innovation. Challenges in financing innovation exist globally and vary depending on each country's economic situation, legislative framework, and financial system.

Companies in the private sector, especially startups looking to develop new technologies, often seek the help of venture capital, crowdfunding or private investors. However, given the high risks and uncertainty, in most cases such financial resources are not enough for small and medium-sized businesses. At the same time, government support, in particular grants and subsidies, has become one of the necessary forms of financing innovation activities.

The study of innovative financing methods and mechanisms, their implementation and the introduction of innovative approaches in the service sector are necessary for the competitive and sustainable development of the country's economy. Analysis of international experience and opportunities for financing existing innovation activities in Uzbekistan is an important step in the development of effective financial mechanisms for the service sector.

2. Innovation activities and financing: theoretical framework.

Innovation activity is the process of developing and implementing a new ideas, products, services or processes. For the service sector, innovation refers to the introduction of new approaches in the fields of technological, organizational and marketing. Innovation helps a company adapt its products or services to market demands, improve operational efficiency, and enhance competitiveness. [1]

When innovating, the main goal is to create high value through new or improved services. This is what contributes to the growth of the company and the development of the economy. Innovations in the service sector, especially digital technology, make it possible to provide customers with high-quality and personalized services. Funding innovation relies on several different mechanisms and sources. These mechanisms, in turn, differ according to the stage of growth of the company, the economic situation of the country, and the industry specifics. [2] The following are the main ways in which innovation activities can be funded:

Equity financing is the use of internal resources (income, profit, reserves) of an enterprise. It is the most common method for small and medium businesses and requires the enterprise to effectively manage its existing resources. The positive point of this method is that it is free of external loans or requirements from investors, but it implies a limited availability of financial resources. Example: Startups and small businesses can use their own funds to promote a product or service. This method allows for more independent decision-making, but limited own funds often prevent large-scale innovation.

Venture capital (VC) is a type of investment used to finance high-risk startups. Venture capital investors typically invest in businesses that operate in innovative industries such as technology, biology, digital services, etc. In this way, investors, through equity, invest in enterprises and get a substantial profit if they are successful. Example: In the US and Europe, the support of venture capital companies has played a key role in the development of new startups, including the formation of global giants such as Uber, Airbnb, etc. This method is particularly effective for startups that have the potential for rapid growth, especially in the development of technological innovations. Crowdfunding is a way to raise a small amount of funds from the general public. It refers to the process of raising funds for innovative projects on Internet platforms (Kickstarter, Indiegogo, and others). In this way, an

enterprise or project provides a service or product to the public when it raises funds in the specified amount. The positive side of financing innovative projects using crowdfunding is the creation of large-scale investor attraction and marketing opportunities. Example: Xiaomi's crowdfunding of its smart phones. In this model, customers are financed by purchasing products in advance. [3]

Government grants and subsidies are an important source of funding for the development of innovative projects and start-ups. States provide various financial programs to stimulate innovation. In Europe, for example, large funds are allocated to various innovative projects through the Horizon Europe program. In this way, the state provides financial resources to achieve its economic and social goals. Example: The EU Horizon 2020 programme has allocated over €80 billion of financial resources for innovative projects in science and technology, including the development of digital and green technologies.

Bank lending is one of the traditional ways of financing innovative activities. Banks provide long-term loans to develop innovative services. However, due to the high risk and uncertainty, some startups and innovative businesses may find it difficult to obtain a bank loan. Digital banks and fintech companies, on the other hand, may be less risky than banks when it comes to financing innovative services. Example: Low interest rate loans offered by banks for innovative startups or special programs (for example, the SBA loan program in the USA). [4]

There are the following main risks and limitations when financing innovation activities:

- Risk and uncertainty: An innovative project or startup will be associated with high risk, as a new idea or technology may justify itself or be different. For investors, this uncertainty can put their capital at risk.
- Financial constraints: For small and medium-sized businesses, limited financial resources can hinder the implementation of innovative activities. Businesses often rely on internal resources, but when they do not have enough funds, it becomes difficult to find external funding.
- Market demand and competition: The success of innovative services often depends on market demand and competitiveness. If new technology or services don't keep up with market demand, they may not be successful.
- The role of the state and regulators: The role of the state in encouraging innovative activities is huge. However, in some cases, limited grants or subsidies provided by the state, or complexity with requests, can limit the innovative activities of enterprises. [5]

3. International experience: Successful models of financing (International Practices of Innovative Financing)

Learning and implementing successful models for financing innovation is of important importance in stimulating economic growth and increasing their competitiveness. Different countries adopt different approaches to implementing innovative financing, which are shaped according to their social, economic and political characteristics. Below we will analyze international practices that have been successful in financing innovative activities. The U.S. is one of the world's leading countries in financing innovation. The U.S. innovation ecosystem plays a key role in the development of high technologies and the support of new start-ups.

In the U.S., Venture Capital (VC) companies are an important source in attracting large capital and funding fast-growing tech startups. VC investments are of utmost importance to innovative startups as they invest their investments in companies that are high-risk but have great growth potential. In the U.S., the venture capital and private equity sectors play a key role in the development of big tech

companies and innovation in the advanced services sector. The Silicon Valley region, for example, as a hub for technology and innovation, is a leader in attracting major venture capital investment from around the world. In the development of new technologies, many startups, such as Google, Facebook, and Tesla, have attracted venture capital investment. In addition, angel investors (large individual investors) in the U.S. also provide financial resources for innovative startups. Angel investors support new businesses, mostly with their own funds. This is especially important for startups, as they will need large external financial resources to launch their projects. [6]

The European Union (EU) has established successful models through enhanced public-private partnerships in financing innovation. The Horizon Europe programme is the EU's largest funding programme for scientific and innovative research and supports research and innovation in EU countries. The Horizon Europe program provides major funding for innovative projects aimed at research, technological development, and the creation of new services in Europe. It is expected that €95.5 billion will be allocated through this program, which is intended for 2021–2027. The program provides large grants and financial opportunities for start-ups, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The EU countries aim to foster technological innovation and green economy through the programme. In addition, EU countries, through the European Investment Fund (EIF), assist in attracting venture capital and private investment for innovative startups. The EIF provides funds for the development of innovative companies and assists in the creation of an innovative ecosystem. [7]

The role of the state in financing innovation activities in China is enormous. The Chinese government will provide a wide range of financial support for the development of innovative technologies. In 2021, the Chinese government allocated \$ 150 billion for technological development, which is leading to an increase in China's role in the global innovation economy.

China has large investment funds called Venture Capital and Private Equity that help grow new tech companies and start-ups.

Crowdfunding and FinTech (financial technology) are also common innovative financing mechanisms in China. The development of fintech platforms in China, such as Ant Group and JD Finance, has created new opportunities in financing innovative services. They are facilitating the raising of capital through microlending and individual investors.

There are also many programs in China to receive government grants and subsidies. Innovative programs such as the InnoPrize, the Torch Program, and others provide financial support for the development of start-ups and new technologies in China. [8]

South Korea has implemented an effective public policy in financing innovation activities and has established a successful model in the development of high-tech companies.

State-owned financial institutions such as Korea Development Bank (KDB) and Korea Venture Investment Corp (KVIC) provide venture capital and grants to innovative startups. The private sector also plays a major role in financing innovation in South Korea. Samsung, LG, and other big companies invest heavily to advance their technological innovation. Public and private partnerships are crucial in fostering an innovative ecosystem in South Korea. [9]

Bangalore, India, as a hub for technological innovation, is driving the development of many venture capital and crowdfunding platforms. In India, there are also grants and subsidy programs provided by the government to help grow start-ups. The Startup India programme is India's premier government programme to support start-ups. Through this program, the state provides investments for the development of new technologies. [10]

4. Financing Innovation in Uzbekistan

In Uzbekistan in recent years significant changes are taking place in the field of financing of innovation activities. Many initiatives are underway by the public, private sector and international organizations to support innovative start-ups and new technologies. Effective financial mechanisms and approaches are being developed to develop the innovative environment in Uzbekistan and to make the national economy more competitive.

The main sources for financing innovation in Uzbekistan are: There are various government programs to support innovation activities in Uzbekistan. The state's resources for financing innovative projects are increasing through initiatives such as the Innovative Development Strategy and State Grants for Startups and Innovative Projects.

For example, the InnoBooster program provides special allocated funds to finance innovative projects, which creates great opportunities for young entrepreneurs and start-ups. Example: Grants and subsidies provided by the Ministry of Innovative Development for start-ups in Uzbekistan are helping many companies to implement their projects. [11]

Government grants will deliver innovative ideas and analysis and monitoring mechanisms have been developed to ensure timely implementation of these projects. The role of the private sector in financing innovation activities is increasing.

Venture Capital (VC) companies and angel investors play a major role in funding innovative startups. Development of VC funds in Uzbekistan is accelerating due to the growing interest in the digital economy and technology, in particular.

Example: In Uzbekistan, new financial institutions such as Uzbekistan Venture Capital Fund focus on financing start-ups and innovative projects. These funds support companies that are high-risk but have great growth potential.

In addition, private investment companies are actively involved in the development of the innovation sector. For example, funds such as Foton Ventures and Ittifaq Venture Fund invest in tech startups and innovative companies in Uzbekistan.

Banks and financial institutions in Uzbekistan practice traditional methods of financing innovation. Banks provide financing for innovative technologies and start-ups through a system of loans, collateral and guarantees. [12].

Large banks in Uzbekistan, such as "People's Bank" and "National Bank of Uzbekistan", have developed special loans and financial programs for innovative sector.

Example: Innovative Bank in Uzbekistan provides special loans and financial assistance to startups and technology companies. It also provides advisory services for young entrepreneurs on attracting foreign investors.

International organizations will also provide financial assistance to finance innovation in Uzbekistan. For example, international financial institutions such as the World Bank, the Asian Development Bank (ADB), and the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) provide grants and loans to promote innovation. Example: The World Bank provides grants and investments for innovative projects in Uzbekistan, in particular for the development of innovations in agriculture and industry. These loans are mainly aimed towards the development of new technologies and industrial modernization. [13]

Conclusion.

Financing innovation activities is becoming one of the most important factors supporting economic growth and technological development in Uzbekistan. Currently, great importance is attached to the development of new technologies and support of start-ups through public, private sector and international financial institutions. Disbursement of grants and investments for innovative projects provides an important basis for the country's transition to a digital economy.

However, existing problems in innovative financing, such as financial risks and lack of specialists, require further refinement of the strategies being put forward in Uzbekistan. Government support and the introduction of new financial mechanisms for financing innovation are necessary, as well as increasing security for investors and entrepreneurs. In this process, the use of international experience, integration of modern technologies and expansion of the network are of great importance for the successful development of innovation ecosystem of Uzbekistan. The service sector has become an integral part of the economy in the 21st century, and its innovative development holds an important high place in the global economy. The lack of the financial resources needed to innovate in this sector remains a serious problem, especially for small and medium-sized businesses. The effective methods and mechanisms for financing innovative activities analyzed in the article, in particular methods such as venture capital, crowdfunding, fintech platforms, and government grants, show that they are important in supporting innovation in the service sector.

Study of international experiences, for example those of the United States, Europe, China, and South Korea, confirms the importance of public-private partnerships in innovative financing. In particular, approaches such as venture capital and crowdfunding work well in funding innovative projects, but these methods involve high risk and uncertainty. Therefore, government grants and subsidies are seen as one of the most important sources of funding for innovative activities. While there are many opportunities for innovation financing in Uzbekistan, there are still many problems and limitations. Effective financing of innovation requires the development of close cooperation between the public and private sectors. Successfully innovation in the service sector can be achieved by further improving innovation mechanisms in Uzbekistan, drawing on global experience and supporting the private sector.

The recommendations presented in the article contribute to the competitive and sustainable development of the country's economy through the development of effective mechanisms for financing innovation for the service sector, strengthening public-private partnership, and using international experience.

List of references.

1. Christensen, C. M. (1997). *The Innovator's Dilemma: When New Technologies Cause Great Firms to Fail*. Harvard Business Review Press.
2. Rogers, E. M. (2003). *Diffusion of Innovations*. Free Press.
3. Gompers, P., & Lerner, J. (2001). *The Money of Invention: How Venture Capital Creates New Wealth*. Harvard University Press.
4. Belleflamme, P., Lambert, T., & Schwienbacher, A. (2014). *Crowdfunding: Tapping the Right Crowd*. Journal of Business Venturing.
5. Knight, F. H. (1921). *Risk, Uncertainty, and Profit*. Hart, Schaffner & Marx.
6. Gompers, P., & Lerner, J. (2001). *The Money of Invention: How Venture Capital Creates New Wealth*. Harvard University Press.

7. European Commission. (2020). *Horizon 2020: A Decade of Innovation and Excellence*. European Commission.
8. Wang, J., & Zhang, Y. (2019). *The Role of Government in Venture Capital Development in China*. Journal of Chinese Economic and Business Studies.
9. Kim, J. (2018). *The Role of State and Private Sectors in South Korean Innovation*. Journal of Korean Economic Studies.
10. KPMG India (2020). *Startup India and the Rise of Venture Capital in India*. KPMG Reports.
11. Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2020). *Innovative Development Strategies and Initiatives*. Tashkent: Ministry of Innovative Development.
12. Uzbekistan Venture Capital Fund. (2023). *Investment Opportunities and Support for Startups*. Tashkent: Uzbekistan Venture Capital Fund.
13. "Innovation Bank" Z. (2022). *Special financial programs for tech startups*. Tashkent: Innovative Bank.